

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL AND CLINICAL ASPECTS OF ANTIBIOTIC-INDUCED DIARRHEA

Buruiană D.,

*student, Faculty of General Medicine, SUMPh "Nicolae Testemitanu"
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

Cobîlțean L.

*Associate Professor of the Department of Gastroenterology
SUMPh "Nicolae Testemitanu"
Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*

Abstract

Antibiotic-induced diarrhea (AID), also known as antibiotic-induced intestinal flora imbalance, is a frequent complication of antibiotic therapy, which occurs shortly or up to 8 weeks after the start of drug therapy and is reported in 5-30% of cases [1]. Antibiotics cause significant disruption of the normal composition and functional attributes of the gut microbiome [2]. The damage to this ecosystem, especially by reducing its diversity of microorganisms, can occur in the long term [3]. AID developed with a higher prevalence in women in the age category 61-70 years, on the background of viral Pneumonia (48.9% of cases) caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, independent of the number of antibiotics previously administered. Diarrhea and abdominal pain are the most common manifestations appreciated in the clinical picture, in contrast fever is less common. Aim of our study was to evaluate the epidemiological and clinical aspects of antibiotic-induced diarrhea.

Keywords: antibiotic-induced diarrhea, *Clostridium difficile*, SARS-CoV-2 virus, intestinal microflora, stool, fever, abdominal pain, antibiotics, hospitalization.

Introduction

The intestinal microflora has a crucial role in maintaining both metabolic and immune homeostasis [4]. Among the major functions it performs, the following stand out: maintaining the integrity of the intestinal epithelium, digestion and absorption of ingested nutrients, efficient regulation of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism, prevention of pathogenic invasion, control of the immune system [5, 12]. Disturbance of the microbiome is the main factor favoring the development of inflammatory and infectious processes in the gastrointestinal tract [6]. Currently, AID is a medical problem with an important epidemiological impact. The clinical picture can take both mild manifestations, such as moderate diarrhea, and a severe evolution that includes pseudomembranous colitis, ileus or toxic megacolon [7, 8, 9]. Coinfection with bacterial pathogens during COVID-19 leads to the administration of broad-spectrum antibiotics, which might severely disturb the normal function and composition of intestinal microflora [11]. Thus, gut dysbiosis caused by high exposure with antibiotics favors association with *Clostridium difficile* infection [10].

Materials and methods

The study included 92 de novo patients with the diagnosis of Enterocolitis caused by *Clostridium Difficile*, treated in the gastroenterology department of the "Timofei Moșneaga" Republican Clinical Hospital, Republic of Moldova, during the years 2020-2021. The average age of the patients is 57.23±3 years (26-82 years). The Enterocolitis caused by *Clostridium Difficile* developed more frequently in women - 49 (53.2%), compared to men - 43 (46.8%). The database of the selected material was processed statistically using Microsoft Excel, EpiInfo 7.2.2.6 and EpiMax Table programs.

Results

Following the analysis of the inpatient records of 92 patients included in the study with the diagnosis of Enterocolitis caused by *Clostridium difficile*, it was identified the antibacterial therapy administered prior to hospitalization. AID was found to develop following both antibiotic monotherapy 27 (41%) cases and antibiotic polytherapy 38 (59%) cases. The previous administration of 2 antibiotics was appreciated in 22 (34%) patients, of 3 antibiotics in 12 (18%) patients, of 4 antibiotics – 3 (5%) patients and extremely rarely 5 antibiotics were administered, respectively they induced Enterocolitis caused by *Clostridium difficile* only in 1 (2%) case.

Pic. 1.

Distribution of patients with Enterocolitis caused by Clostridium Difficile according to the number of antibiotics.

The most frequently administered Meropenem, Imipenem, Ciprofloxacin and Ceftriaxone. More rarely, Enterocolitis caused by Clostridium Difficile has been caused by administration of Cefoperazone, Gentamicin, Amoxicillin, Azithromycin.

30 years, 41-50 years, 61-70 years and over 71 years. Men in the age category of 51-60 years developed AID more frequently. With the same frequency, regardless of gender, the disease was recorded in patients whose age was 31-40 years.

According to our study, AID developed with a higher prevalence in women in the age categories 18-

Pic. 2. DAI frequency distribution according to age and gender.

In our study, we found that AID developed most frequently on the background of viral Pneumonia (48.9% of cases) caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, both considered as major healthcare issues. Patients also presented comorbidities including chronic diseases of gastrointestinal tract (n=60), ischemic cardiomyopathies (n=53), type 2 diabetes (n=21), but also oncological affections (n=9). Association of comorbidities with older age and prolonged hospitalization leads to a higher risk of complicated evolution of Clostridium difficile infection [11].

Diarrhea manifested by increasing the frequency of defecation acts and/or the fluidity of faecal matter was appreciated as the most frequent symptom appreciated in the patients included in the study. In most patients it was one of the causes of alteration of the quality of life and reason for seeking medical assistance. According to the results of the coprological exam, in 45 (90%) cases stool malfunction was mentioned: in 31

(62%) patients the stool was unformed, in 14 (28%) patients the stool was slurry and only in 3 (10%) cases the stool was formed.

Abdominal pain was also one of the specific symptoms of AID, being appreciated in 84 (91.3%) patients, but of different intensity from discomfort to intense pain. Other clinical manifestations that accompanied diarrhea and abdominal pain in patients with antibiotic induced diarrhea where abdominal bloating (65.2%), nausea (14,1%) and ascites (13%).

In contrast to the previously presented clinical manifestations, fever at the time of hospitalization was present in only 13 (20%) patients. In 5 patients, the temperature of 37.6-38.5⁰ was maintained. Fever higher than 38.6⁰ was present in 8 patients.

Conclusion

Antibiotic induced diarrhea developed with a higher prevalence in women in the age category 61-70 years, on the background of viral Pneumonia (48.9% of

cases) caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, independent of the number of antibiotics previously administered. Diarrhea and abdominal pain are the most common manifestations appreciated in the clinical picture, in contrast fever is less common.

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